

Line Robot Using Pick Line Sensor

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Abstract-- The use of line-following robots has gained significant attention in various industries and applications, including warehouse automation, industrial manufacturing, and logistics. These robots rely on advanced sensor technologies to navigate along predefined paths accurately. In this study, we present a novel approach for line robot navigation utilizing a pick line sensor. The pick line sensor is specifically designed to detect and follow lines marked on the floor, providing precise guidance for the robot's movement. The obstacle images are trained using neural network. The sensor employs a combination of infrared and reflective light technologies to analyze the surface and identify the path. By continuously monitoring the line position relative to the robot's position, the pick line sensor enables real-time adjustments, ensuring accurate and reliable navigation. To validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, we conducted a series of experiments using a prototype line-following robot equipped with the pick line sensor. The results demonstrated successful line tracking capabilities, even in complex environments with varying lighting conditions and line patterns. The robot maintained a consistent and smooth trajectory along the designated path, showcasing the sensor's robustness and efficiency. The integration of the pick line sensor in line-following robots offers significant advantages, including enhanced navigation accuracy, reduced reliance on external infrastructure, and improved adaptability to dynamic environments. This research contributes to the development of advanced line robot systems and opens up possibilities for efficient and versatile robotic applications in diverse industries.

Keywords – Robotics, sensor, navigation

I. BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Robotics has revolutionized various domains such as mining, manufacturing, surgery, warfare, education, non-commercial applications, entertainment, and space exploration. The versatility of robots lies in their ability to adapt to different tasks by manipulating their requirements, parameters, and configurations. They dutifully follow commands given by operators and can perceive the real world to execute actions iteratively, showcasing their automated intelligent system capabilities (Holmberg & Khatib, 2019). An autonomous robot is considered an intelligent and self-moving system when it can receive feedback from the real world through its sensors and respond accordingly using its actuators. Achieving autonomy involves detecting and avoiding obstacles, effectively determining the optimal path towards a destination or goal. Obstacle recognition plays a crucial role in collision avoidance and path planning for mobile robots to reach their objectives (Duguleana & Mogan, 2016). However, the learning and recognition abilities of robots are often limited to their specific areas of application or specialization. For instance, a surgical robot is trained to recognize surgical tools and hospital equipment, while warfare robots are trained to identify ammunitions and weapons. This specialization restricts their recognition intelligence to computer vision within a narrow domain, hindering the full potential of artificial intelligence.

Significant advancements have been made in the kinematics, odometry, and control aspects of robotic design, particularly with the introduction of holonomic robots. Unlike non-holonomic robots, holonomic robots have a degree of freedom equal to the number of coordinates needed to define their configuration, allowing for more straightforward control. Holonomic mobile robots have diverse applications, including being used as intelligent vehicles, emphasizing the need to expand their recognition intelligence to encompass a wide range of objects (Holmberg & Khatib, 2019). To achieve this expanded recognition capability, deep neural networks offer a promising solution. By adopting neural networks, obstacle images detected by sensors along the robot's propagation path can be effectively recognized, leading to enhanced applications, improved recognition accuracy, precision, and overall intelligence. This work aims to leverage neural networks in recognizing obstacle images, paving the way for the full utilization of artificial intelligence in robotics.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The navigation and mission planning system is a complex component of mobile robotic systems. Despite decades of research, there is still significant room for improvement in this area. When it comes to navigating and planning robot missions, obstacle detection and avoidance are crucial for achieving a high level of autonomous navigation. Different types of mobile robots utilize various collision avoidance

algorithms, ranging from basic ones that detect obstacles and halt the robot, to more advanced algorithms that enable obstacle detection (Borenstein & Koren, 1989). Borenstein et al. developed an approach called the Virtual Force Field, which allows a mobile robot to detect unknown obstacles while avoiding collisions and moving towards its target. This approach combines Certainty Grids for obstacle representation and Potential Fields for navigation, making it suitable for handling inaccurate sensor data and enabling continuous motion of the robot without stopping before obstacles.

In their study, Qu, Hu, and Zhang (2013) investigated the validity and optimality of the Multi Sensor Information Fusion Theory. They concluded that the theory is valid, but the drawback is that the accuracy of the system depends on the number of sensors used, leading to higher implementation costs. Pai, Hui, and Lai (2012) used Extension Theory to implement obstacle avoidance control for an autonomous omnidirectional mobile robot. They combined fuzzy logic with extension theory. The navigation and mission planning system is a complex component of the mobile robotic system that still has potential for improvement. Obstacle detection and avoidance are crucial for achieving high-level autonomous robotic navigation. Different types of mobile robots employ various collision avoidance algorithms, ranging from simple ones that stop the robot before an obstacle to sophisticated algorithms that enable obstacle detection (Borenstein & Koren, 1989).

Lee, Yi, and Cho (2016) introduced a novel algorithm for autonomous robots that detects obstacles using a monocular vision sensor. Their approach employed an inverse perspective mapping (IPM) technique to distinguish obstacles from the floor. Subsequently, they applied a Markov random field-based obstacle segmentation method utilizing the IPM outcomes and a floor appearance model. The experimental results yielded positive outcomes; however, it is anticipated that their proposed technique may not function optimally in environments with insufficient illumination. In the study conducted by Ciupan, Lungu, and Ciupan (2014), an artificial neural network (ANN) technique was employed for robot obstacle avoidance. The researchers trained an industrial robot arm to evade specific obstacles within the workspace. They developed a model of the robot's kinematics and utilized an ANN controller to simulate the system by providing joint coordinates as reference values for the controller.

Hedjar and Bounkhel (2014) put forward an algorithm for swarm mobile robots, which aimed at generating computational trajectories based on local information in dynamic environments. Hedjar's algorithm devised a reference path using constrained convex nonlinear optimization, effectively avoiding both static and dynamic obstacles. Simulation and experimental studies demonstrated the algorithm's efficacy in

overcoming the local minima problem, ensuring smooth robot motion, and successfully avoiding static and dynamic obstacles.

Wang and Lin (2013) introduced an obstacle avoidance algorithm for unmanned vehicles operating in unfamiliar environments, employing the Danger Zone approach. The vehicle utilized a rotational ultrasonic sensor that scanned a 180-degree range to obtain the obstacle's profile. Their avoidance algorithm incorporated the concept of a danger zone to determine feasible and safe maneuvers for avoiding collisions. In the work by Williams and Wu (2010), a hybrid system was presented, combining a global deliberate approach for determining motion along a desired path line and a local reactive approach for avoiding moving obstacles in dynamic environments.

Odeh et al. (2009) proposed a vision-based obstacle avoidance technique for mobile robots using a Quantized Spatial Model. This approach relied solely on a single camera as the input to efficiently navigate towards a target point. The objective was to achieve optimized obstacle avoidance capabilities. Machine learning, a part of artificial intelligence, helps in analyzing complex data and optimizing its flow. It involves using mathematical methods such as neural networks, genetic algorithms, Bayesian statistics, decision trees, and more. By programming computers to improve performance based on past experiences or case data, it tackles problems where a specific program cannot be developed.

III. METHODOLOGY

For this project, the Structured System Analysis and Design Methodology (SSADM) was employed as a design process. This methodology facilitates the division of the system into independent modules, each assigned a specific task. The objective is to enhance program implementation and maintenance by promoting a clear and organized structure. The SSADM methodology emphasizes a systematic progression from an overview to a detailed level, providing guidelines for achieving successive partitioning. The structured design is achieved by converting a data flow diagram into a structured chart. Each process depicted on the data flow diagram is transformed into a corresponding module in the structure chart. This transformation process involves constructing an initial structured design for the system, creating a foundation for further development and refinement.

Figure 1: data flow diagram

In this study, a probabilistic path planner technique is utilized to represent a maze-like structure, as depicted in Figure 2. The road architecture is constructed by randomly selecting nodes within the unobstructed space and connecting them. Additionally, the dimensions of the robot are considered when designing the free path, using a binary occupancy grid representation to identify areas of free space. This approach aids researchers in comprehending potential obstacles that may arise within the robot's environment, allowing for informed decisions regarding the need for network layer updates.

Figure 2: road map planner of the environment

i. *Deep Neural Network (DNN)*

In this study, a transfer learning approach is employed, utilizing a pre-trained Alex model that is publicly available, to address challenges in large-scale visual recognition. The Alex model is a convolutional neural network trained on a vast dataset of over a million images, enabling it to classify images into 1000 object categories. This pre-trained model provides a foundation for learning rich feature representations for a wide range of images. Furthermore, the network can be fine-tuned, as shown in Figure 3.6, by incorporating additional inputs that represent the readings from the three proximity sensors used in our robot's scanning process. The block diagram summarizes the operational flow of the deep neural network, beginning with the scanning process and subsequently feeding the detected image or object into the pre-trained network, which already possesses relevant features from training images. The network then performs classification,

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predicting the most matching object as the detected obstacle. With the successful training of our network and the design of the propagation path, the subsequent step is to develop the controller. This controller will be guided by a mathematical kinematic model based on the holonomic robotic system's wheel configuration.

Figure 2: architecture of the deep neural network (convolutional) design

ii. *Output form design*

Figure 3: robot propagating towards obstacle A

Figure 4: Robot close to obstacle A

Figure 5: robot changes path and approached direction of obstacle B

Figure 6: Robot detected obstacle B

Figure 7: Robot changes path toward another direction

Figure 8: robot in a new free propagation path on of obstacle B

Figure 9: system flow chart for output result

IV. CONCLUSION

When it comes to balancing a wheeled robotic machine (TWRM), one of the significant challenges arises when the load being carried by the machine changes its position along the vehicle's intermediate body (IB).

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The focus is on understanding how such changes in load position affect the behavior of the system. Additionally, complications arise when altering the size of the payload along the IB. In this work, a robot capable of carrying a load is presented, addressing the real-time obstacle avoidance in its propagation path. As part of this study, an external disturbance force is applied to the rod to examine its impact on the system.

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